

PECULIARITIES OF PHONETIC STYLISTIC DEVICES IN POETRY

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Abstract. This article discusses peculiarities of phonetic stylistic devices in poetry. Examples from poetry are given in this research work and they are of great importance for learning stylistics

Key words: syntactical level, ellipsis, asyndeton, parallelism, inversion.

The sentence, as a unit of a certain level, is a sequence of relatively independent lexical and phrasal units (words or word combinations), and what differentiates a sentence from a word is the fact that the sentence structure is changeable; it does not have any constant length: it can be shortened or extended, complete or incomplete, simple, compound or complex. Besides, its constituents, length, word-order, as well as communicative type: assertion, negation, interrogation, exhortation are variable [3]. So, to analyze the sentence stylistically on the syntactic level, we will admit that most common and currently used are two-member sentences containing subject and predicate and perhaps, some secondary elements, having normal word order and the function. Syntactic expressive means and stylistic devices of the English language:

An elliptical sentence is such a syntactic structure in which there is no subject, or predicate, or both. The main parts of elliptical sentences are omitted by the speaker intentionally in cases when they are semantically redundant.

***You curled the papers from your hair,
Or clasped the yellow soles of
In the palms of both soiled hands.***

In poetry, the omission of words whose absence does not impede the reader's ability to understand the expression. For example, Shakespeare makes frequent use of the phrase "I will away" in his plays, with the missing verb understood to be "go." T.S. Eliot employs ellipsis in the following passage from "Preludes" [1].

The possessive "your" is left out in the second and third lines, but it can be assumed that the woman addressed by the speaker is clasping the soles of her own feet with her own hands [2]. Ellipsis saves the speaker from needless effort, spares his time, reduces redundancy of speech. Elliptical structures may also reveal such speakers' emotions as excitement, impatience, delight, etc. As a stylistic device, ellipsis is an effective means of protagonists' portrayal.

***Rest at pale evening ...
A tall, slim tree ...
Night coming tenderly Black like me.***

In the poem "Dream Variations," Langston Hughes uses ellipses to indicate a dreamy trailing-off, a kind of pause in rhythm that lets the reader take a moment to picture the dream he describes [3]:

These are very famous lines from "Stopping by the woods in the snowy evening" of Frost. Here the person is standing in the snowy evening along with his horse. He is pondering at the beauty of surrounding when his horse alarmed him. He is ready to go back because he has to perform worldly duties and tasks. Here through repetition, the poet wants to express his devotion towards his responsibilities and also gives rhythm to the lines [2].

Parallelism is a stylistic device of producing two or more syntactic structures according to the same syntactic pattern:

We real cool.
We Left school.
We Lurk late.
We Strike straight.
We Sing sin.
We Thin gin.
We Jazz June.
We Die soon

The parallel structures in the poem “We real cool” by Gwendolyn Brooks” give it a little waltz and jingle feel. Each parallel sentence follows a basic pattern, starting with pronouns and ending with nouns and adverbs, except the first line, which ends with an adjective [1].

Syntactic parallelism is polyfunctional. It creates rhythm and is typical of poetry. It makes speech persuasive and is a feature of the publicist and oratory styles. It underlines important information and is widely used in everyday speech. Parallel structure creates fluency in writing and enhances readability, as it uses patterns of words in a way that readers can easily follow, and relate them to each other. It makes language appear refined, especially in writing and advertising. It also lends consistency to professional writing, as it provides rhythm and balance that lead the readers to the exact idea, without any misguidance. In addition, parallel structures synchronize, repeat and emphasize the words and thoughts of the writers.

In conclusion, the aim of this study was to analyze phonetic stylistic devices and expressive means in poems as well as to analyze which functions, they carry out in poems. What’s more, the results yielded by the data analysis and the benefits of literature received positive perceptions. It is suggested that the analysis of linguostylistic means should be made clear to people who are studying stylistics at the very early of the course.

References:

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